

Virtual microbes in a holographic bio-system

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Abstract: To control micro-organisms in bio-systems, a holographic model is proposed. In this proposal, virtual micro-molecules could be produced through two ways. In first method, a macro-light source with the shape of a micro-organism could be built. This source emits some waves which collide with lenses of a microscope, return and induce micro-image of desired object. Microbes interact with this image as a real micro-molecule. One can test this idea by using a multi-gonal lamp and a microscope. It is observed that the shape of lamp is induced in any micro-bubble. In second method, using two light sources for a microscope in a dark lab, two waves with different colors are emerged. Light waves take shape of microbes, collide with lenses, return and produce virtual microbes. These microbes could deceive real bacteria and micro-organisms and control them. Using these techniques, some infectious diseases could be cured.

Keywords: Holography; Virtual; Microbes; Bio-systems; Control

I. Introduction

Up to date, effects of light waves on micro-organisms and bacteria have been known extensively. Some microbes like photosynthetic and phototropic bacteria use of light waves in process of building food and storing energy [1,2]. The process of absorption of light and its applications within the structure of these micro-organisms have considered in many works. For example, some authors have studied the variety of light-harvesting (LH) structures present in phototrophic prokaryotes. This investigation has provided an overview of the LH complexes of purple bacteria, green sulfur bacteria (GSB), acidobacteria, filamentous anoxygenic phototrophs (FAP), and cyanobacteria [3]. Another research has argued that main antenna complex for light-harvesting, LH2 in purple bacteria,

contains two rings of identical bacteriochlorophyll pigments, B800 and B850, absorbing at 800 and 850 nm, respectively. It has been an unsolved problem why static disorder of the strongly coupled B850 ring is several times larger than that of the B800 ring. This group has shown that mixing between excitons and charge transfer states in the B850 ring is responsible for the effect [4].

Besides these special bacteria, other types of bacteria also may be affected by light waves. A group has considered different methods for programming bacteria by light sensors. They have introduced engineered light sensors in bacteria and their applications, including tuning synthetic circuits and achieving feedback controls over microbial cell culture [5]. Another team has reviewed the methods for killing bacteria by using light instead of biocides. They have highlighted the recent development of the photothermal bactericidal surfaces which can convert light energy into thermal energy to effectively eliminate bacteria through various hyperthermia effects [6]. Another investigators have compiled the published data on bacterial inactivation caused by visible light and endogenous photosensitizers. They have shown that visible light has strong disinfectant properties, a fact that is not well known in comparison to the antibacterial properties of UV light [7].

Reverse to these results, some researchers have shown that light enhances the growth rates of natural populations of aerobic anoxygenic phototrophic bacteria. They have found that these bacteria display higher growth rates when incubated under light-dark cycles than in complete darkness [8]. In parallel, in other paper, effects of light-dark cycles on photosynthetic bacteria wastewater treatment and valuable substances production have been considered. They have shown that varying light-dark cycles achieved higher substances yields at given energy [9].

In addition to these applications, light waves could be used in imaging so. There are several types of microscopes (like fluorescence microscope and two-photon microscope) which each of them play a role in imaging and detecting microbes. Fluorescence microscope uses fluorescence to generate an image, whether it is a more simple set up like an epifluorescence microscope or a more complicated design such as a confocal microscope, which uses optical sectioning to get better resolution of the fluorescence image [10,11]. Unlike traditional fluorescence microscopy, in which the excitation wavelength is shorter than the emission wavelength, there is another type of microscope which uses simultaneous excitation by two photons with longer wavelength than the emitted light. This two photon excitation microscope uses a [fluorescence](#) imaging technique that allows imaging of [living tissue](#) up to about one millimeter in thickness. [12].

In addition to special microscopes, there also some methods which use of light and specially two photons in detecting bacteria and other microbes. For example, a group has introduced a two-Photon-Active Organotin(IV) Complexes for Antibacterial Function and Superresolution Bacteria Imaging [13]. Another team has argued that a small-molecule with large two-photon action cross-section could be used as the membrane-permeable probe for live cells imaging and bacteria viability [14]

Now, the question arises that how we could use of light waves in controlling microbes? To response this question, we propose a two photon technique to produce a holography and deceive microbes.

II. Materials and Method:

A: Materials:

1. A light microscope
2. Two light sources with different colors
3. A light source with special shape
4. Slide
5. Two samples of microbes (We have produced two systems by using microbes which live on a leaf)

B: Method:

1. To test the first proposal, we have used of a multi-gonal lamp (See figure 1). This lamp is formed from several light sources which each of them could act like a source for a microscope.
2. We put a leaf on the slide, pour some liquid on it and consider motions of micro-bubbles and microbes under a light microscope.
3. We use of a multi-gonal lamp instead of normal light source in a microscope.
4. We analyze the change in micro-bubbles after using a multi-gonal lamp.

5. Light waves take shape of their sources, collide with lenses of a microscope, return and induce their shapes in each micro-bubble (See figure 2)
6. To test second proposal, we use of two light sources in a dark lab. One light source is the normal lamp in a microscope and second light source could be located near it. Colors of two lights should be different. We used of blue and yellow colors (See figure 3).
7. Two light waves with different colors take shape of microbes, collide with lenses of a microscope, return and produce virtual microbes (See figure 4).
8. We took some videos and pictures of events under the microscope in each stage.

Fig 1: A multi-gonal light source

2. Induction of multi-gonal shapes within the micro-bubbles by using a multi-gonal lamp

Fig 3. Two light sources for producing holography in a dark lab

Fig 4: Induction of virtual microbes by using holography in a dark lab

III. Results :

1. We used a multi-gonal lamp as the light source for the microscope. Emitted waves took shape of their sources, collide with lenses of the microscope, return and induced virtual image of that light source within any micro-bubble (See figures 5 and 6).
2. If we placed multi-gonal lamp with another source which its shape is closed to the shape of a special microbe, we can produce virtual microbes. These microbes could be regarded as real microbes by biological system and help us in curing diseases.

3. At second stage, we used of an extra lamp as the second light sources in a microscope. This new lamp had different color respect to the light of normal lamp. These two lamps emit two waves in a dark lab. These waves took shape of micro-objects, collide with lenses, return and produce virtual micro-molecules.
4. Each microbe had a virtual shape which sometimes interact with it (See figure 7)
8. Another interesting result is that other microbes also interact with virtual shapes near the real microbes. It seems that these virtual micro-objects act like a bridge between real microbes (See figure 8).

Fig 5: Induction of the shape of light source within micro-bubbles under a light microscope (First picture)

Fig 6: Induction of the shape of light source within micro-bubbles under a light microscope (Second picture)

Fig 7. Induction of virtual micro-molecules by using two lamps with different colors

Fig 8. Interaction between microbes with virtual shapes

Discussion:

In this article, we have shown that by several mechanisms, one can induce virtual microbes and control real micro-organisms. This idea could be used for controlling bacteria and infectious diseases. In fact, using the holographic method, some virtual microbes could be induced in human/s body and make it ready to defense in front of real microbes. Also, virtual microbes could interact with real microbes and prevent of their attacks to cells.

Conclusion

In this research, using the holographic model, two proposals for producing virtual microbes and deceiving real micro-organisms have been proposed. In one technique, a light source with the shape of desired micro-molecules have been build. This source induced desired shape in any micro-bubbles on the slide under a light microscope. In second technique, two light sources with different colors were used. These light waves took shape of micro-molecules on a slide under a microscope, collide with its lenses, return and produce virtual micro-objects. These virtual micro-molecules deceive ral microbes and could control them. We can use of this technique to cure some diseases.

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